

Significance of absolute phase in matrix logarithm methods for obtaining the birefringence and dichroism parameters of a nondepolarizing medium

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Abstract

State of a nondepolarizing optical medium is characterized by birefringence and dichroism parameters, L , L' , C and the associated Mueller matrix can be written as a commutative product of a matrix Z and its complex conjugate ($M=Z^*Z=ZZ^*$). Z matrix has an exponential form in terms of the parameters L, L', C , and these parameters can be directly read from the matrix logarithm of Z . In general, Z matrix is arbitrary up to a phase factor, f , and $fZ(fZ)^*$ yields the same Mueller matrix for any f . But matrix logarithm of Z is sensitive to f , i.e., $\log Z$ is not equal to $\log(fZ)$, in general. In this note it is shown that, for some values of f , $\log(fZ)$ leads to states that cannot be achieved by the Mueller matrix logarithm.

Introduction

Any nondepolarizing Mueller matrix can be written as a commutative product of a complex \mathbf{Z} matrix and its complex conjugate of [1, 2]

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z} \quad (1)$$

Any \mathbf{Z} matrix is characterized by four complex anisotropy parameters (τ, α, β and γ), and it is defined as

$$\mathbf{Z} = e^{\mathbf{z}} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{z} in the exponent is another matrix defined in terms of χ, L, L' and C ;

$$\mathbf{z} = -\frac{i}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \chi & L & L' & -C \\ L & \chi & iC & iL' \\ L' & -iC & \chi & -iL \\ -C & -iL' & iL & \chi \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$. Details can be found in the Appendix.

If \mathbf{Z} matrix is given, χ , L , L' and C can be directly read from the matrix logarithm of \mathbf{Z}

$$\log \mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{z} \quad (4)$$

However, \mathbf{Z} matrix is arbitrary up to a phase. $e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z}$ generates the same Mueller matrix for all θ . But, matrix logarithm of \mathbf{Z} is sensitive to the phase angle θ , and this property has some theoretical consequences.

Since, $\log(\mathbf{Z}) \neq \log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$, \mathbf{Z} and $(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ give rise to different sets of parameters L, L' and C . Let S_0 be the set given by $\log \mathbf{Z}$ and let $S_+(S_-)$ be the set given by $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ in an interval centered around $\theta = \pi$ that subtends an angle equal to the absolute value of the real part of T , where T is the complex angle ($= \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$). On the other hand, S_0, S_+ and S_- generate the same Mueller matrix and Mueller matrix logarithm gives back only S_0 . Neither S_+ nor S_- can be found from the matrix logarithm of the Mueller matrix.

As an example let \mathbf{Z} be the matrix corresponding to a quarter-wave plate with parameters $\tau = 1/\sqrt{2}$, $\alpha = i/\sqrt{2}$, $\beta = \gamma = 0$:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{2} & i/\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 \\ i/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \\ 0 & 0 & -1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

At $\theta = 0$, $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ gives $S_0 : \{L = -\pi/2, L' = 0, C = 0\}$, which corresponds to the state with $T = -\pi/2$. As we increase θ , $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ continues to give S_0 if $\theta < 3\pi/4$. But, at $\theta = 3\pi/4$, $\log(e^{i\theta})$ jumps to the state $S_+ : \{L = 3\pi/2, L' = 0, C = 0\}$, which corresponds to $T = -\pi/2 + 2\pi$. In an interval $3\pi/4 \leq \theta \leq 5\pi/4$, $\log(e^{i\theta})$ gives S_+ state, and when $5\pi/4 < \theta < 2\pi$ $\log(e^{i\theta})$ gives S_0 state.

As a second example let \mathbf{Z} be the matrix corresponding to a quarter-wave plate with parameters $\tau = 1/\sqrt{2}$, $\alpha = -i/\sqrt{2}$, $\beta = \gamma = 0$:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{2} & -i/\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -i/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{2} & -1/\sqrt{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1/\sqrt{2} & 1/\sqrt{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

At $\theta = 0$, $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ gives $S_0 : \{L = \pi/2, L' = 0, C = 0\}$, which corresponds to the state with $T = \pi/2$. As we increase θ , $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ continues to give S_0 if $\theta < 3\pi/4$. But, at $\theta = 3\pi/4$, $\log(e^{i\theta})$ jumps to the state $S_- : \{L = -3\pi/2, L' = 0, C = 0\}$, which corresponds to $T = \pi/2 - 2\pi$. In an interval $3\pi/4 \leq \theta \leq 5\pi/4$, $\log(e^{i\theta})$ gives S_- state, and when $5\pi/4 < \theta < 2\pi$ $\log(e^{i\theta})$ gives S_0 state.

In analytic inversion methods, S_+ and S_- states are obtained by adding or subtracting 2π from T artificially, on the other hand, $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z})$ gives S_+ or S_- in a natural way.

In practice the Mueller matrix comes first. \mathbf{Z} can be calculated from the normalized Mueller matrix; let us call this matrix \mathbf{Z}_m . $\log \mathbf{Z}_m$ gives S_0 and $\log(e^{i\theta}\mathbf{Z}_m)$ gives either S_+ or S_- ; but, $\log(\mathbf{M})$ gives only S_0 . As explained before, there exists an interval such that, inside and outside the interval $\log \mathbf{Z}_m$ gives $S_+(S_-)$ and S_0 respectively.

Appendix

Analytic inversion of \mathbf{Z}

\mathbf{Z} matrix is defined in an exponential form in terms of the spectroscopic parameters, isotropic phase retardation (η), isotropic amplitude absorption (κ), circular dichroism (CD), circular birefringence (CB), horizontal and 45° linear dichroism (LD and LD'), horizontal and 45° linear birefringence (LB and LB'):

$$\mathbf{Z} = e^{\mathbf{z}} \quad (7)$$

\mathbf{z} in the exponent is another matrix defined in terms of χ, L, L' and C ;

$$\mathbf{z} = -\frac{i}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \chi & L & L' & -C \\ L & \chi & iC & iL' \\ L' & -iC & \chi & -iL \\ -C & -iL' & iL & \chi \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$.

Series expansion of $e^{\mathbf{z}}$ gives

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \alpha & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\tau = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \alpha = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\beta = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL'}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \gamma = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iC}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (11)$$

with $T = \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$. From the calculated values of τ, α, β and γ we can go back to birefringence and dichroism parameters by first calculating the reverse angle $T_r/2$. Then, the analytic inversion algorithm reproduces the retrieved values of χ_r, L_r, L'_r, C_r :

$$T_r/2 = \text{atan}\sqrt{-(\alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \gamma^2)/\tau^2}, \quad \chi_r = 2i\ln(\tau \sec(T/2)) \quad (12)$$

then

$$L_r = \alpha T_r q, \quad L'_r = \beta T_r q, \quad C_r = -\gamma T_r q, \quad (13)$$

where, $q = i \cot(T_r/2)/\tau$. This method is equivalent to the analytic inversion of the Mueller-Jones matrix given in [3, 5].

Higher and lower orders of L, L', C corresponding to any value of n can be calculated from the simple relations:

$$L_n = \frac{T_n}{T_0} L_0, \quad L'_n = \frac{T_n}{T_0} L'_0, \quad C_n = \frac{T_n}{T_0} C_0. \quad \text{Or,} \quad \frac{T_n}{T_m} = \frac{L_n}{L_m} = \frac{L'_n}{L'_m} = \frac{C_n}{C_m} \quad (14)$$

where $T_n = T_0 + n2\pi$, $T_m = T_0 + m2\pi$ with $m, n = \{\dots - 3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, and T_0, L_0, L'_0, C_0 are the parameters belonging to $n = 0$ state.

Matrix logarithm of Mueller matrix

If the Mueller matrix is given, we can also calculate L, L' and C directly from the matrix logarithm of the Mueller matrix [6]. Since, \mathbf{z} commutes with \mathbf{z}^* , any nondepolarizing Mueller matrix can be written as [7]

$$\mathbf{M} = e^{\mathbf{z}} e^{\mathbf{z}^*} = e^{\mathbf{z} + \mathbf{z}^*} \quad (15)$$

Therefore,

$$\log \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{z}^* \quad (16)$$

Explicitly,

$$\log \mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Im}(\chi) & \text{Im}(L) & \text{Im}(L') & -\text{Im}(C) \\ \text{Im}(L) & \text{Im}(\chi) & \text{Re}(C) & \text{Re}(L') \\ \text{Im}(L') & -\text{Re}(C) & \text{Im}(\chi) & -\text{Re}(L) \\ -\text{Im}(C) & -\text{Re}(L') & \text{Re}(L) & \text{Im}(\chi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Real and imaginary parts of the birefringence and dichroism parameters can be read from $\log \mathbf{M}$.

Obtaining \mathbf{Z} from the Mueller matrix

If we want to begin with an experimental nondepolarizing Mueller matrix or with a Mueller matrix that generated by $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*$, we can find the corresponding \mathbf{Z} matrix by transforming \mathbf{M} into the Cloude's coherency matrix \mathbf{H} [8]:

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{i,j=0}^3 m_{ij} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^*), \quad (18)$$

where m_{ij} are the elements of \mathbf{M} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$ are the Pauli matrices with the 2×2 identity matrix $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0$ in the following order:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Since we have assumed that the Mueller matrix of the system is nondepolarizing, the associated \mathbf{H} matrix will be of rank 1, and the derived values of τ, α, β and γ can be directly read from the elements of any non-zero column of \mathbf{H} . The values of τ, α, β and γ derived from the Mueller matrix may differ by the same constant factor from the original inputs, but this does not affect the results of the matrix logarithm of \mathbf{Z} .

References

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